

Research article (Featured theme: Geolinguistic approach to Sino-Tibetan)

Current issues and perspectives on Yi characters: From the past and into the future

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Abstract: This paper aims first to show current issues in the study of the Yi characters, then to demonstrate the high affinity between geolinguistics and the study of the Yi characters as well as the efficaciousness of a geolinguistic approach when many issues can be solved by mapping the Yi characters.

Yiyu (彝語) is the language of the Yi ethnic group living in the southwestern part of China, and the northern parts of Vietnam and Laos. Yi people possess their own script and to date have written a great number of manuscripts so far. Due to the huge dialectal differences, and various changes throughout history, there has come to be an enormous disparity among the Yi characters in their shape, phonetic values and meaning from region to region. As a result, these characters are mutually almost incomprehensible among the dialects.

Therefore, in the Yi-character study, there exist such issues as clarifying the change patterns in the Yi script and detecting possible routes of its spread, and these puzzles have attracted the interest of many scholars. The author hence applied the geolinguistic approach to tackling them by mapping as many Yi characters of all regions as possible. As a result of these efforts, certain features and tendencies have been found in the Yi-character change patterns, and the chronological order in several graphemes.

However, at the same time, this attempt also suggests the necessity of analysing the Yi characters in a much narrower area to elucidate details of their change process and the directions of spread more precisely and accurately. Accordingly, in this paper, the Yi characters written in *Hua-Yi Yiyu (Chinese-Foreign Glossaries)* are geolinguistically analysed, because the places of the data sources in these glossaries are located in a relatively narrow area where Sichuan, Guizhou and Yunnan intersect. This study is preliminary but effective in solving some of the current issues of the Yi-character study.*

Keywords: the Yi script; Yi-character maps; geolinguistic approach; *Hua-Yi Yiyu*

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1. Introduction

First, I will provide you with a brief introduction to Yiyu (彝語), the language of the Yi ethnic group, and the Yi script.

1.1. Yiyu and the Yi script

Yiyu is the language of the Yi ethnic group. It belongs to the Lolo-Burmese language group of the Tibeto-Burman language family. It is spoken in the southwestern part of China, in areas included in the provinces of Sichuan, Guizhou, Yunnan, and Guangxi, as well as northern areas of Vietnam and Laos. Map 1 shows approximately the entire area where the Yi ethnic group live.

Map 1 The area where the Yi ethnic group reside.

According to the official classification of languages in China, there are six Yi dialects: Northern, Eastern, Southern, Southeastern, Western, and Central. Four of them – i.e., the Northern, Eastern, Southern, and Southeastern dialects – possess the Yi script and manuscripts written in it. No script has so far been reported as being used among the Yi people in Vietnam and Laos.

Map 2 Distribution of the six Yi dialects in China and the approximate area with the Yi script¹.

Map 2 indicates the distribution of the Yi dialects in China. The area shaded in blue demonstrates the dialects possessing the Yi script and manuscripts.

Yi characters are basically all syllabic. However, they probably used to be logographic. It is said that Yi characters were created around the time of the Yuan or Ming dynasties.

Bimos, religious leaders among the Yi people, have dealt with the script and manuscripts exclusively within their clan throughout history, basically from father to son. Yi characters have been used within *Bimos* to keep secrets like religious scriptures. Therefore, from the point of view of the *Bimos*, the characters were not a tool for communication but were used instead for the prevention of any leakage of their clan's heritage. In such circumstances, the *Bimos* quite freely used a homophonous character or a character with very similar phonetic value, and they often ignored such differences in tones or voicedness in consonants in their writing. They also sometimes freely added certain alternations to characters as long as they could understand what was written. In other words, the Yi characters can be said to be very personal.

¹ The original map was retrieved from Nishida (1979: 182).

As a result of such high individuation, exclusiveness, broad spread of the script, and possible lexical changes, the characters in each area or village came to show great diversity in their shapes, phonetic values, and meaning.

1.2. Current issues in the study of Yi characters

There are several important current issues in the study of the Yi characters. As mentioned above, the Yi characters show great diversification in shapes and phonetic values (presented in Chart 1), due to the regional differences or processes or degrees of phonological or semantic changes.

Consequently, it is not easy to determine the chronological order among the dialects and to trace the route of their propagation. Also, elucidating the patterns of changes in the Yi characters is a knotty problem.

Chart 1 The Yi characters meaning ‘this’ in four dialects.

1.3. Compatibility between geolinguistics and Yi-character study

As explained above, the critical issues in the Yi-character study begin with the history of Yi characters, as follows:

- Possible route(s) by which Yi characters would have spread
- Patterns in which Yi characters have changed

Contemplating these issues, I struck upon a novel idea that drawing Yi-character maps and analysing them geolinguistically might help to solve these hard issues. Here is the reason why I chose this path.

These issues are related to the history of the Yi characters. Then, geolinguistics is one of the methods in clarifying the history of a language. Geolinguistics aims at revealing the direction of language changes². Geolinguistic principles and aims seem to match very well with sorting out the current issues in Yi characters.

² Sibata (1969: 11) mentions as follows: 「……言語地理学は言語史の方法の一つである。したがって、言語地理学の目的は言語の歴史を明らかにすることにある。……」 (“Geolinguistics is one of the methods in studying language history. Therefore, geolinguistics aims at elucidating the history of a language...”: translated by the author.)

2. Geolinguistic approach to Yi-character study

In this section, I will trace how the geolinguistic approach can be applied to Yi-character study and what it has revealed to us so far.

2.1. Main research conducted by the author

One of the studies of Yi characters in which the geolinguistic approach was applied is Iwasa (2018a).

First, a map was drawn by picking up from all resources I have with as many Yi characters as possible. See Map 3 as an example.

Map 3 Yi-character map for the meaning of '1'.

Second, I pick up a key character, sometimes a few key characters. These key characters are determined mainly from the perspective of the character shape, as the logographic nature of the Yi characters is respected.

Third, I observe the whole distribution of the characters and attempt to find how and why the characters show such a spread. At the same time, I also search if there is a substitution of homonyms or any other features. (See Map 4 below, for example.)

Map 4 A result of geolinguistic analysis of Map 3 (Iwasa, 2018a: 15).

In Map 4, the characters regarded as belonging to the same group are indicated by the same colour, namely red, blue, or green. Several research results will be presented in the next section.

2.2. What the study has yielded to us so far

In this section, I will introduce three main research results (chiefly from Iwasa, 2018a).

2.2.1. Substitution of homonyms

Here is an example of the substitution of homonyms, or phonetic loans. In Map 5, you can see the characters in the red frame and those in the blue circles. Both show formal and phonetic resemblances. These characters originally meant ‘arrow’, but it seems that they began to be used for expressing ‘many’ because of their phonetic similarity. (See Iwasa, 2018a for more details.)

Map 5 Yi-character map for the meaning of ‘many’ (Iwasa, 2018a: 10).

2.2.2. AB distribution

There are several maps showing AB distribution. One of them is shown below, Map 6. In this map, some characters in the red shade (group A) can be in the same continuum, whereas the character in the blue shade (group B) might also be included. It is very hard to determine which group (A or B) is older just judging from the map. In this case, more investigation into the continuum is needed to figure out their feasible metamorphoses.

Map 6 Yi-character map for the meaning of ‘rope’ (Iwasa, 2018a: 62)³.

2.2.3. ABA distribution

Next, we have an example of ABA distribution. In Map 7, you can see two red circles. Let’s call them A. You can also see a blue circle, which we can call B.

ABA distribution is thought to imply that the characters in A could be anticipated to be relatively older than the characters in the blue circle, B area, although it is still difficult to affirm it immediately. What we can find from this map is at least the probability that in the B area a new change could have happened, because it would be improbable that the same innovation could coincidentally happen in two remote locations, namely the unconnected A areas.

³ Some amendments have been made to the original map for clarity by the author.

Map 7 Yi-character map for the meaning of ‘to stand’ (Iwasa, 2018a: 49)⁴.

Map 8 Yi-character map for the meaning of ‘month’⁵.

⁴ Some amendments have been made to the original map for clarity by the author.

⁵ This map was drawn for this paper by the author.

3.1. Urgent tasks in the Yi-character study

My previous studies on the Yi characters have proven that a geolinguistic approach is effective and practical in clarifying their change patterns and possible routes of their spread.

However, to elucidate more accurately the change patterns in the character shapes and possible spread routes of the script, it is urgently necessary to analyse the data of the Yi characters in a much narrower area. For this purpose, studying and mapping the data in *Hua-Yi Yiyu* (華夷譯語) is a very desirable attempt⁷.

Hua-Yi Yiyu is a series of Chinese–Foreign Glossary books compiled during the Ming and Qing Dynasties and contains five books on the vocabularies of distinctive Yi dialects and scripts. These five dialects are thought to have been located in a relatively narrow area where Sichuan, Guizhou, and Yunnan intersect. The locations of three of them are identified, whereas the rest are still open to question.

Hua-Yi Yiyu also gives us the phonetic information of the Yi characters by the phonetic transcriptions written in Chinese characters. It helps to detect the two unknown places mentioned above and to observe phonological changes that happened in all locations throughout history, even though it contains many discrepancies between the Yi characters and their phonetic transcriptions⁸.

In the next section, I will introduce my current geolinguistic analysis of the Yi characters in *Hua-Yi Yiyu*.

3.2. Current challenge: Geolinguistic exploration of the Yi characters in *Hua-Yi Yiyu*

Here I will show several results from my preliminary geolinguistic exploration into the Yi characters written in *Hua-Yi Yiyu*.

3.2.1. Mapping the Yi characters written in *Hua-Yi Yiyu* and comparing them with the existing Yi-character maps

The materials used for mapping the Yi characters from *Hua-Yi Yiyu* are as follows⁹:

- ① *Gugong Book, the third version, Yongning shu Shuiliao Luoluo Yiyu* (故宮本第三種 永寧屬水潦猺獮譯語): The basic data are based on Nishida (1979).
- ② *Gugong Book, the second version, Jianchang shu Shamaliangshan ge Luoluo Yiyu* (故宮本第二種 建昌屬罵梁山各猺獮譯語): The basic data are based on Matsukawa and Nie (2015).

⁷ Based on the present study, the author has developed the data and findings then written a paper (Iwasa 2023) with the entire data on the Yi languages recorded in *Hua-Yi Yiyu*.

⁸ These errors can have several causes. I will mention them in detail on another occasion due to the limited space available in this paper.

⁹ When I started this research, the whole reproduction of the five books of *Luoluo Yiyu* was not available. That is why I referred only to these three data sources. In my paper, Iwasa (2023), all five versions are analysed.

- ③ *Gugong Book, the first version, Dongchuan-fu shu Luoluo-Yiyu* (故宫本第一種 東川府屬猥獮譯語): Information provided as a courtesy.

I have collected the data of the regions indicated in the map below and drawn the Yi-character maps prior to this exploration. The main data sources for these existing maps are Yi-Chinese dictionaries. See the References for more details.

Map 10 The locations of the existing Yi-character maps.

The locations of the data from *Hua-Yi Yiyu* are shown below in Map 11. The numbers on Map 11 correspond to which of the versions of *Hua-Yi Yiyu*, ①, ② or ③, mentioned earlier at the beginning of this section, was the source. These locations on Map 11 are illustrated on the right side of Map 12 to 16.

Map 11 The locations of the data from *Hua-Yi Yiyu*.

3.2.1.1. ‘SKY’

Here are maps for ‘SKY (天)’. The left map shows the Yi characters from *Hua-Yi Yiyu*, while the right one shows the Yi characters in the whole area. The right map was drawn previously by the author. I have indicated each grapheme by using a distinctive colour – red and blue – that we can observe if the characters from *Hua-Yi Yiyu* correspond to those on the right map. We can also examine the phonetic values by comparing the pronunciations of the modern Yi dialects on the right map and the phonetic transcriptions in *Hua-Yi Yiyu* on the left – for example, ‘麼迷’, ‘木’, and ‘母’.

Map 12 The Yi characters indicating ‘SKY’.

The characters indicated by both red and blue seem to be in the same continuum, but focusing more minutely on their shape, they can be divided into two groups, namely, the red group and the blue group. On both maps, the characters shaded in red bear a strong resemblance to each other, while those in blue also do. Therefore, it can be said that the characters recorded in *Hua-Yi Yiyu* reflect the regional characteristics very well.

Additionally, the transcriptions of Chinese characters in *Hua-Yi Yiyu* also seem to correspond very well to the pronunciations in the modern dialects. For example, on the left map, the transcription ‘麽迷’ in Jianchang – a locale very near Xide on the right map – might be pronounced like [mɤ mi] in disregard of the tones, if its pinyin ‘me mi’ is taken into consideration. This phonetic value [mɤ mi] is similar enough to [mo³³ m³³] in Xide on the right map.

3.2.1.2. ‘STAR’

As you can see on the left map of Map 13, there are three graphemes in *Hua-Yi Yiyu*. The Yi characters on the right map correspond well with them formally and geographically as well.

We also find that the graphemes shaded in red, and the ones in blue seem to have a strong relation to each other. Although they should be treated as allographs of one particular grapheme, they are regarded as distinctive because the shape of any parts and/or the number of strokes obviously appear to be different.

Then, the grapheme shaded in yellow may have been derived from the same grapheme as the rest. For example, this grapheme may have been simplified through time and changed towards the graphemes as shaded in red and blue. In particular, the characters shaded in both red and blue seem to show a certain state of transition phase from the yellow-shaded ones.

Map 13 The Yi characters indicating 'STAR'.

3.2.1.3. 'SNOW'

Map 14 gives us more concrete information about the change patterns of the Yi characters throughout history. All characters on both maps should probably be interrelated and illustrate their process of the formal transition. To clarify each phase of the transition, I will set three graphemes and observe their spread.

The character of Shuiliao on the left map, which is shaded in red, is similar to those of Panxian and Shiping on the right map, which are also marked by red shades.

Then, the characters shaded in yellow seem to intervene with the red ones. The ones in yellow shade may be more innovative than those in red.

The characters shaded in blue are found in the most peripheral areas, they hence might have once spread across a vast area.

Map 14 The Yi characters indicating 'SNOW'.

3.2.1.4. 'EARTH'

On Map 15, each grapheme of the left map corresponds well to the distribution of the characters on the right map. Whereas the word forms around Jianchang are different from the others, the rest show a high resemblance to one another.

Except for the character in the pink circle around Longlin, the characters spread from Zhaotong to the southernmost area around Shiping, both shaded and unshaded, appear to be interrelated judging from the curious similarity in their forms and pronunciation.

Map 15 The Yi characters indicating 'EARTH'.

3.2.1.5. ‘WATER’

Map 16 shows very well the correspondence of the distribution of each grapheme. The grapheme shaded in yellow is the most widely spread on the right map. The one shaded in red can be treated as an allograph of it.

Very interestingly, the character in the pink circle at Longlin demonstrates a very different form from the others. This needs close and thorough investigation.

Map 16 The Yi characters indicating ‘WATER’.

3.3. Final remarks and future perspectives in the Yi-character study

To sum up, from the maps, we have found that the Yi characters written in *Hua-Yi Yiyu* demonstrate a high level of resemblance to those on the existing Yi-character maps according to the region and that the Yi characters in Longlin may bear different features from those in other regions.

Hence, in the next phase of this study, we need to examine the process of the metamorphoses of the Yi characters in *Hua-Yi Yiyu* by comparing them to the existing Yi-character maps. We also need to analyse the transcriptions by Chinese characters and reconstruct the phonetic values of the Yi characters in *Hua-Yi Yiyu*. Needless to say, it is undoubtedly necessary to refer to all five versions of *Hua-Yi Yiyu* in that case. Because two of the five locations of *Hua-Yi Yiyu* are unknown, this study will contribute to locating them in space.

This paper demonstrates that a geolinguistic approach has proved to be efficacious for the historical study of the Yi characters. I hope that geolinguistic analysis of all the Yi characters written in *Hua-Yi Yiyu* will lead us to the elucidation of their change patterns and possible spread routes as soon as is feasible.

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